

TECHNOLOGIES FOR INTELLIGENT GEOSPATIAL MODELLING OF SECURITY RISK ASSESSMENT FOR TERRITORIAL COMMUNITIES: THEORETICAL APPROACHES**Mamonov K.,**<http://orcid.org/0000-0002-0797-2609>**Nesterenko S.,**<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5124-9728>**Shterndok E.,**<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1107-7401>**Viatkin R.**<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8807-9988>*O.M. Beketov National University of Urban Economy in Kharkiv, Ukraine*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19493920>**Abstract**

The relevance of the research topic regarding the justification of theoretical approaches to the development of intelligent geospatial modelling technology for assessing the security risks of territorial communities has been proven.

The following theoretical approaches to determining the security risks of territorial communities are proposed: functional (characterised by the directions and features of the emergence of security risks of territorial communities); stakeholder (interested parties interacting in the system of territorial communities are identified, whose interaction leads to the emergence of security risks); military (special attention is focused on the consequences of aggressive military actions that affect the security of territorial communities); structural (characterised by elements that form security risks for territorial communities); factorial (factors influencing security risks are identified); quantitative (a basis is formed for developing solutions regarding the emergence of and countering security risks using mathematical, geoinformation, and artificial intelligence tools); systemic (characterised by a set of functional, stakeholder, spatial, environmental, investment, and military factors that affect the security risks of territorial communities, have a structure, and are determined by the formation of a quantitative basis for countering them using mathematical, geoinformation, and artificial intelligence tools).

To ensure the functioning and development of territorial communities, a technology for intelligent geospatial modelling of security risk assessment for territorial communities has been proposed. The presented technology includes the following stages: analysis of the external and internal environment; formation of information and analytical support for the emergence of security risks for territorial communities; construction of spatial support; identification of factors affecting security risks; construction of a multi-level system of indicators affecting security risks; development and application of a method for assessing the level of security risks; mathematical and geoinformation modelling of factors; formation of a monitoring system; development of scientifically based recommendations to improve the effectiveness of countering security risks to territorial communities.

Keywords: *security risks, territorial communities, spatial provision, assessment, technology, intelligent geospatial modelling, geographic information systems.*

Relevance of the study. Contemporary transformation processes determine the change in the security paradigm of territorial communities (TC). Significant challenges related to overcoming the consequences of hostilities, the imbalance of regional and stakeholder relations, ecocide, the growing risks to information security, the disruption of land and property complexes of territorial communities, and the pollution of territories require the development and application of modern technologies, the formation of a theoretical basis, and the improvement of regulatory and legal support.

Territorial communities are an important element of the local self-government system, where most of the economic processes and social trends that affect the quality of life and livelihoods of the population are formed and implemented. Therefore, counteracting the emergence of risks to the security of TC is an important socio-economic task that affects the development of regions and the state.

It is important to identify problems that can be solved with the help of geographic information systems

(GIS) for security at the state level and for territorial communities. In recent years, regulatory and legal provisions have been adopted to promote the development of GIS: the Law of Ukraine «On the National Geospatial Data Infrastructure» and Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine № 532-2021-p «On Approval of the Procedure for the Functioning of the National Geospatial Data Infrastructure». At the same time, there are unresolved issues regarding the implementation of the presented support in relation to the emergence and counteraction of security risks in territorial communities using geographic information systems.

In order to form an information security framework, there are problematic issues regarding ensuring its completeness and reliability. In this context, the use of artificial intelligence tools is a pressing task. Thus, the topic of research on the justification of theoretical approaches to the development of intelligent geospatial modelling technology for assessing security risks in territorial communities is relevant and of great importance.

Review of literary sources. Existing scientific studies lack a unified theoretical approach to determining TG security risks. The financial aspects of ensuring security and the emergence of corresponding risks in territorial communities are the focus of studies [1–3]. The emergence of social and economic security risks for TC should be noted [1, 4, 5]. The emergence of security risks affects the territorial development of land use by local communities, which is characterised in the works [6, 7].

The authors address issues relating to the application of geographic information systems in the field of spatial planning and development, and land use [8, 9].

Thus, based on theoretical principles, this study has identified a lack of sufficient justification and a lack of systematic approach in the formulation of theoretical principles and methodologies for defining intellectual geospatial modelling of security risk assessment for local communities, and in the development of the relevant technology.

The aim of this study is to develop theoretical approaches to the creation of a technology for intelligent geospatial modelling of security risks in local communities.

Main part. The conduct of aggressive military operations influences the emergence of security risks. In the military sphere, the Delta system serves as a significant practical foundation—a Ukrainian situational awareness platform that integrates data from UAVs, satellites, sensor networks and intelligence, helping to map the combat situation in real time [10].

Security in Ukraine is paramount to the survival and existence of the state. To achieve success in this area, it is essential to keep pace with global technological developments and advance in the same direction, ensuring competitiveness in today's world. The current state of the legislative framework dedicated to security issues is quite extensive: the Constitution of Ukraine, the Civil Protection Code of Ukraine, the Laws of Ukraine «On National Security of Ukraine», «On the Fundamentals of National Resistance», «On the Legal Regime of Martial Law», «On High-Risk Facilities», «On Occupational Safety», «On Environmental Protection», «On the Use of Nuclear Energy and Radiation Safety», «On the Protection of Persons from the Effects of Ionising Radiation», «On Information», «On the Protection of Information in Information and Telecommunications Systems», «On the Basic Principles of Ensuring Ukraine's Cybersecurity», «On State Secrets», «On the National Police», «On the Security Service of Ukraine», «On the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine», «On the State Service for Special Communications and Information Protection of Ukraine». It should be noted that whilst these laws acknowledge the necessity of information technologies to facilitate security activities, they do not directly address the use of GIS as a security tool.

Security risks faced by local communities in relation to the development and maintenance of their resilience. It should be noted that resilience is characterised by the ability to counter internal and external threats [11].

Resilience is characterised as a system's ability to

respond to disturbances and reorganise itself during times of change, whilst essentially maintaining the same function, structure and feedback loops, and thus its identity; that is, the ability to change in order to preserve its identity; resilience is a dynamic concept that focuses on how to withstand change and how to evolve alongside it [12].

The identified threats affecting the functioning of local communities:

- in the administrative and governance sphere: competition over powers between local self-government bodies and military administrations; staff shortages due to insufficient funding, the mobilisation of local government employees, and the emigration of skilled personnel; lack of clear coordination between different levels of government;

- in the social sphere: mass population migration (both internally displaced persons and external emigration); rising social tensions between local community residents and internally displaced persons; declining trust in local authorities;

- in the financial sphere: a decline in revenue due to the transfer of certain taxes from the local to the state budget; the imposition of additional costs to provide social guarantees;

- in the infrastructure sphere: physical destruction of critical infrastructure; lack of resources for the restoration and construction of protective structures [13].

The functional aspects and tools for countering negative phenomena arising in local communities are highlighted in [14].

Identified risks to the spatial development of local authorities The identified risks to the spatial development of local authorities [15].

The identified risks arising from the hostilities and affecting the functioning of local communities [16].

Thus, the following theoretical approaches to identifying security risks for local communities are proposed:

- *functional*: this approach identifies the areas and characteristics of the emergence of security risks for local communities;

- *stakeholder-based*: this approach identifies the stakeholders involved in the system of local community activities, whose interactions give rise to security risks;

- *military*: particular attention is focused on the consequences of aggressive military operations affecting the security of territorial communities;

- *structural*: characterises the elements that constitute security risks for territorial communities;

- *Factor-based*: factors influencing security risks are identified;

- *Quantitative*: a framework is established for developing solutions regarding the emergence of and countering security risks using mathematical, geoinformation, and artificial intelligence tools;

- *systemic*: characterised by a combination of functional, stakeholder, spatial, environmental, investment and military factors that influence the security risks of territorial communities; these factors have a structure and are defined by the formation of a quantitative basis for countering them using

mathematical, geoinformation and artificial intelligence tools.

Conclusions. Consequently, to ensure the functioning and development of local communities, a technology for intelligent geospatial modelling of security risk assessment for local communities has been proposed. This technology comprises the following stages: analysis of the external and internal environment; development of an information and analytical framework for identifying security risks to local communities; construction of spatial support; identification of factors influencing security risks; construction of a multi-level system of indicators influencing security risks; development and application of a method for assessing security risk levels; mathematical and geoinformation modelling of factors; formation of a monitoring system; development of scientifically grounded recommendations to enhance the effectiveness of countering security risks in territorial communities.

References:

1. Volosiuk, M., & Sirenko, I. (2021) Economic security of the territorial community in the system of providing its sustainable development. *Economics and the State*, 6, 105–109. <https://doi.org/10.32702/2306-6806.2021.6.105>
2. Kraynik, O., & Fedorchak, O. (2022) Financing the development of local communities in the context of decentralisation. *Financial and credit activity problems of theory and practice*, 2(43), 118–125. <https://doi.org/10.55643/fcaptop.2.43.2022.3558>
3. Novak, N. (2022) Management of financial and economic security of united territorial communities in Ukraine on the basis of tax administration. *Agrosvit*, 3, 3–9. <https://doi.org/10.32702/2306-6792.2022.3.3>
4. Hrubliak O., & Zhavoronok A. (2024) Features of the financing of social services under the conditions of decentralization. *Scientific innovation and cutting-edge technology*, 2(30), 783–795. [https://doi.org/10.52058/2786-5274-2024-2\(30\)-783-795](https://doi.org/10.52058/2786-5274-2024-2(30)-783-795)
5. Rybak, H., & Fedotova, J. (2023). Economic security of the regions of Ukraine in the process of decentralization. *International Science Journal of Management, Economics & Finance*, 2(1), 56–64. <https://doi.org/10.46299/j.isjmef.20230201.06>
6. Mamonov, K., Meteshkin, K., Shterndok, E., & Kovalchuk, V. (2025) Spatial planning for regional land use development: approaches to formulation and assessment. *Roads and road construction*, 118(1), 156–166. http://publications.ntu.edu.ua/avtdorogi_i_stroitelstv o/118.1/156.pdf
7. Mamonov, K., Kovalchuk, V., Tkachuk, V., & Kovalov, D. (2025) Developing scenarios for regional land use planning. *Municipal Economy of Cities. Series: Technical Sciences and Architecture*, 1(189), 325–330. <https://khg.kname.edu.ua/index.php/khg/article/view/6485/6405>
8. Mamonov, K., Frolov, V., Kasyanov, V., & Yevdokimov, A. (2025) Geoinformation support for soil condition in the territorial organisation system. *Roads and road construction*, 118(2), 138–147. http://publications.ntu.edu.ua/avtdorogi_i_stroitelstv o/118.2/138.pdf
9. Nesterenko, S., Shterndok, E., & Pyshna, A. (2025) Geoinformation support for land-use planning. *Roads and road construction*, 117(2), 251–258. http://publications.ntu.edu.ua/avtdorogi_i_stroitelstv o/117.2/251.pdf
10. Delta (situational awareness system) https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Delta_%28situational_awareness_system%29?utm_source.com
11. Manyena, B., Machingura, F., & O’Keefe, P. (2019) Disaster Resilience Integrated Framework for Transformation (DRIFT): A new approach to theorising and operationalising resilience. *World Development*, 123. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0305750X19301639?via%3Dihub>
12. Folke C. (2016) Resilience (Republished). *Ecology and Society*, 21(4), 44. <http://www.ecologyandsociety.org/vol21/iss4/art44/>
13. Steshenko, T., Krechek, A., & Kryvets, O. (2025) Resilience of territorial communities in Ukraine. *Scientific Bulletin of Uzhhorod National University. Law Series*, 88(1), 197–202. <https://visnyk-pravo.uzhnu.edu.ua/article/view/328929/318655>
14. Norris, F., Stevens, S., Pfefferbaum, B., Wyche, K., & Pfefferbaum, R. (2008) Community resilience as a metaphor, theory, set of capacities, and strategy for disaster readiness. *American Journal of Community Psychology*, 41(1–2), 127–150. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18157631/>
15. Zayats, T. (2023) Modernisation of development planning for local authorities in wartime. *Effective Economy*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.32702/2307-2105.2023.7.1>
16. Relocation programme: 800 companies have «relocated» in the first year of the war. *Ekonomichna Pravda*, 2023. <https://www.epravda.com.ua/news/2023/03/2/697630/>